

THE USAGE OF PROPER NAMES IN PHRASEOLOGY

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The present article is devoted to the study of the stages of history and development of phraseology in world linguistics, which contains culture-related information. It was divided into several periods according to Soviet, modern Russian and foreign scientists. They transmit significant information about the range of issues that arose during the study of typology of phraseological dictionaries. The theoretical part of this article deals with the problems of recording phrases and idioms in dictionaries. The investigation of the development phrases in phraseology helps to identify the specifics of understanding phraseology, history of phraseological dictionaries, and their use nowadays in world linguistics. The article investigates the interrelation between culture and phraseological units including proper names on the base of the English, Russian and Kazakh languages. The topicality of the research article is determined by: 1) continued interest in learning various relations of language, thinking and culture as well as representation mechanisms of stereotypes in language; 2) integration tendencies of research paradigms in linguistics, in particular systematic and functional approaches; 3) constant tendency to order the system of expressive means in language; 4) trinity of Three Language Policy (the Kazakh, Russian and English languages) 5) multilingualism and its effect on peoples linguistic worldview. The article states several definitions of the term stereotype in modern linguistics thus emphasizing its significance and multiversity. To indicate the reflection of history and culture in language the etymology of a number of set phrases is given as well. Methodological base of the research paper is formed by the system of fundamental representations of general interrelation of language and thinking, language and person, language and culture and their interdependence. The basic methods of the research paper are methods of linguistic observation and description which intend to interpret peculiarities of the investigated language units, an explanatory method and component-semantic analysis. It should be noted that the analysis has been conducted in an integrated way by using the methods appropriate to the given aim and tasks on each stage of the work. General scientific base of the paper is formed by principles of anthropocentrism, systematization and determinism.

Michael J. Evans and Rainer Wimmers views [“Searles theory of proper names, from a linguistic point of view”] There has been a long and great tradition, in philosophy as well as linguistics, of inquiry into the functions proper names fulfil in any linguistic community. Philosophical questions differ in many respects from what linguists are interested in and from what they think to be relevant for the ordinary and everyday use of proper names. Philosophers attention is strongly focused on the question of what role proper names have to play in relating facts of the actual world to linguistic expressions, often called linguistic signs by linguists.

We do not want to say that the main questions which philosophers usually think of as constituting the “problem of proper names” (namely questions about the possible referential use of proper names) have not been treated exhaustively in language philosophy. On the contrary, as far as we can see, the problem of reference by means of proper names has been extensively discussed, so that there is hardly any conceivable aspect which has not been considered and reconsidered [cf. Schwayder 1961 passim; Linsky 1967 passim]. But the purely referential function is not the only one that proper names have in a natural language. Other aspects of these names are important for linguists, as we show below, but philosophers, including Searle, do not pay much attention to them. Consideration of at least some of these

other phenomena, while possibly raising a few more problems for the language philosopher, would certainly help towards a better appreciation of the nature of proper names, and promote interdisciplinary understanding also.

There is a widely accepted and prominent definition of a proper name. That given in Frege (1966, 54) says that any linguistic expression counts as a proper name, provided that it is used to designate one and only one definite object. A linguistic expression can have any one of a large variety of different forms. It can be an individual's name like Fred or Baker, it may contain no name, but instantiate the grammatical structure of a noun phrase (NP), as in the tallest man in our town or the woman I met yesterday at 12 o'clock. Of course, several variations of this conception of proper name exist in the literature (cf. Wimmer 1973, 77 ff.). However, they all emphasize that there should be a single definite object designated by a proper name and that there should be established and fixed relation between the linguistic expression and the object meant.

In contemporary philosophical thinking on the problem of proper names we still find the reflections of a continuing tradition following on from Frege's view. Russell's analysis of proper names, being within the tradition, is compatible with Frege's view. Where Searle comments on proper names, he focusses on their referential function. Though he has a more restricted conception than Frege of what constitutes a proper name, his disregard for the differentiations that linguists have proposed on the syntactic and semantic complexity of proper names puts his theoretical work within the philosophical mainstream of the last hundred years. All these aspects of Searle's theory of proper names can be regarded as uncontroversial from a linguistics viewpoint. No linguist nowadays has any doubt that there is at least some connotative, historical/etymological or social content associated with the use of common names.

The thrust of Searle's argument on descriptive content is mainly directed against Kripke's theory of "causal chains" (cf. Kripke 1980), which says that in fixing the reference of a name, there might be room for a descriptive or predicative content securing the act of baptism or naming, but that — from the moment the referent is fixed — there is only a causal or communicative chain which secures the correct use of a proper name. In short: the fixed referential relation between a name and a certain object is transported only by direct communication from one speaker to another, almost without using any intermediate descriptions.

From a linguistic point of view, there is no contradiction between Searle's and Kripke's positions, but only a difference of interest. Kripke is mainly interested in the act of fixing the reference, whereas Searle wants to emphasize that some descriptive content always remains to help secure what one might call a "fully consummated reference". The treatment of proper names in linguistics is somewhat different. To begin with, the objects which linguists taxonomize as "proper names" form a large number of sets related to each other in quite complex ways, so that proper names might be regarded as itself a name for a superset.

This fact is further complicated by the presence of two linguistic labels, proper names and proper nouns, which have sometimes been used synonymously in the literature and sometimes not, a tradition which in the logical treatment of grammar goes back at least as far as Thomas Wilson (1551) or the even earlier semantic classification of nouns adumbrated in Linacre (1533) (cf. Padley 1976, 41). Ultimately, it depends on the polysemy of the Greek word *onoma*, found in the work of the second-century B. C. grammarian Dionysius Thrax. This fact is further complicated by the presence of two linguistic labels, proper names

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Proper names play an important role in our understanding of linguistic aboutness or reference. For instance, the name-bearer relation is a good candidate for the paradigm of the reference relation: it provides us with our initial grip on this relation and controls our thinking about it. For this and other reasons proper names have been at the center of philosophical attention. However, proper names are as controversial as they are conceptually fundamental. Since Kripke's seminal lectures *Naming and Necessity* the controversy about proper names has taken the form of a debate between two main camps, descriptivists and non-descriptivists like Kripke himself.

Descriptivists hold that there is a close connection between proper names and definite descriptions: the meaning or sense of a proper name can be given by a (bundle of) definite description(s). The satisfier, if any, of the definite description(s) that provide(s) the meaning of a proper name is its referent. Descriptivists can allow for empty proper names that are meaningful. They also have an initially plausible account of true informative identity statements (Marilyn Monroe is no one other person than Norma Jean Baker). Their informativity is grounded in a difference in meaning-giving descriptions.

Kripke presents several arguments against the descriptivist view. He famously observed that a proper name of *x* and definite descriptions satisfied by *x* cannot be substituted without change of truth-value in modal sentences. He provided further the outline of an alternative view or picture of reference, according to which proper names are tags first introduced in a baptism and then transmitted from speaker to speaker in a communicative chain. Kripke's arguments did not end, but rather fuel, the discussion about proper names. If he is right, the semantic significance of a proper name is exhausted by its referent. How can, then, an empty proper name be meaningful? How can an identity sentence in which proper names flank the identity sign be informative? Since descriptivists have answers to these questions, this view has not been given up in the face of Kripke's arguments. Rather descriptivists have refined it in order to incorporate Kripke's observations. For example, there are different ways to conceptualize the modal difference between proper names and definite descriptions that are compatible with the spirit of descriptivism. In the next round, non-descriptivists started to assess the drawbacks of these ways of conceptualizing the phenomena. So far no solution has emerged. Rather, the strengths of one view are the weaknesses of the other. How can one make philosophical progress in understanding proper names in this situation? Our aim with the conference *Proper Names: Philosophical and Linguistic Perspectives* (Göttingen, September 2011) was to bring linguists and philosophers together to investigate proper names from different perspectives. We are pleased to publish the proceedings of the conference in this special issue. Here is a brief overview of the contents of our volume.

Kripke suggested to his readers a picture of reference, according to which the reference of a proper name is determined by a causal chain. However, he did not develop his picture in detail. In his *Reference without Referents* (2005) Sainsbury took up the topic where Kripke left off. He provided an account of name-introduction and reference-transmission that

was designed to make room for empty proper names. Sainsburys contribution “The same name” contains an outline and defence of a causal view, but now it is a causal view of proper name individuation and not reference determination that allows one to distinguish different, but co-spelled proper names. Sainsbury argues that a plausible version of the causal view will allow one to see empty proper names as meaningful, Stephen Barkers “Expressivism about reference and Quantification over the Non-Existent without Meinongian Metaphysics” explores a different response to the problems posed by empty proper names. He argues in his paper that prima facie empty names in fact refer to non-existent objects and that we also can quantify over such objects. However, he thinks we can hold such a view without commitment to an ontologically serious conception of non-existent objects as proposed by Meinongians. According to Barker, an expressivist conception of reference is all that we need to make such a view palatable.

Kenneth Taylors “Names as Devices of Explicit Co-reference” develops an interpretation of the explanatory role of Kripkes communicative chains that shares with Sainsburys new view the assumption that these chains have the function to individuate names. In opposition to Sainsbury, Taylor thinks that these chains also determine the reference of a name. Furthermore, he defends the view that these chains should be interpreted as anaphoric chains of reference preservation and they, hence, not only determine the reference of a name, but also play a vital role to solve Freges puzzle. Taylor distinguishes between explicit or obvious co-reference from accidental co-reference. “Hesperus” and “Phosphorus” are accidentally co-referential: given how the non-linguistic facts are, these singular terms refer to the same object and necessarily so. However, different tokens of the same proper name are explicitly co-referential. That proper names not only refer, but that tokens of the same name obviously co-refer is a suggestion that can inform our understanding of the kind of expression a proper name is.

Kamp and Maier are mainly concerned with the implementation of certain aspects of Kripkes view into the formal semantic framework of Discourse Representing Theory. Kamp makes use of a conception of external and internal anchors and so-called labelled entity representations to capture certain important semantic and cognitive aspects of proper names pointed out by Kripke. In opposition to Kripke, Kamp avoids any commitment to communicative causal chains that connect different meaningful uses of proper names. Instead, Kamp proposes a mental network of anchored labelled entity representation that account for the meaningful communication with proper names about specific objects. Such networks allow us to determine the referent of a name in a way that is parasitic on the existence of the entity representations of other people, but they also allow a competent speaker to gain an expert status and, hence, determine the referent of a name in a way that is not deferential.

Emar Maier argues in his contribution “Reference, binding, and presupposition: three perspectives on the semantics of proper names” for the main thesis that proper names are definite expressions that trigger presuppositions. He makes use of the general treatment of presuppositions in a DRT framework proposed by Geurts and van der Sandt and aims to implement proper names into such a framework. According to him, there are rigid and non-rigid uses of proper names and he aims to account for these different uses of names by making use of Hunters conception of an extra embedding level in a Discourse Representing Structure (DRS) called hyperglobal DRS. A hyperglobal DRS content plays a role similar to Kamps “internal anchors”, that is, their content is to be interpreted with respect to a fixed context

parameter, distinct from the evaluation parameter. This technical adaption of the mentioned DRT framework for the representation of presuppositions allows one to account for anaphoric and non-anaphoric uses of proper names in semantic terms. Proponents of the causal chain view take proper names to be singular terms that at most refer to one object. But common sense has it that there are many Peter Smiths. How can, then, Peter Smith be a singular term? An influential response to this problem is Burges predicate view of proper names that logically represents proper names as general terms that can be combined with different overt and covert determiners (the, this). The following contributions investigate this view from different perspectives.

In short, proper names seem to be those linguistic entities most specifically suited to fulfil and guarantee an unmistakably established and constant relation between a given phenomenon in the world on the one hand, and a linguistic sign or the use of a linguistic sign on the other. What the relation is between the world and a language or, more specifically, certain signs of a natural language, has been the dominant question in the philosophy of proper names for the last century (cf. Dummett 1973, 54ff). John R. Searle has made important and prominent contributions to the solution of this problem (cf. Searle 1969, 157ff; 1983, 231 ff). His proposals for describing and defining the function of proper names in a natural language have been widely accepted by linguists.

In linguistics, and especially in the field of onomastics there has been a serious lack of reflection on the theoretical problems associated with proper names (for the situation in Germany, see e. g. Debus 1980), so that proposals made by Searle and other philosophers have been readily welcomed, at least as a basis for further discussion. In the following remarks on Searles theory of proper names from a linguistic point of view, we shall try to pay due heed to the fact that the issue has for a long time been dominated by philosophical questions and aims. These questions and aims will not be disparaged as minor or irrelevant from our linguistic point of view; but it will be necessary to say that a linguistic treatment of proper names requires a somewhat different view of the topic than philosophers usually supply.

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